

Tuning Constraint-Based Communication in Distributed Problem Solving

Francesca Arcelli¹, Uwe M. Borghoff³, Ferrante Formato², Remo Pareschi³

¹ Dipartimento di Ingegneria dell' Informazione e di Ingegneria Elettrica
Università di Salerno. I-84084 Fisciano (SA), Italy.

Email: arcelli@udsab.dia.unisa.it

² Centro di Ricerca in Matematica Pura e Applicata (CRMPA)
Salerno. I-84084 Fisciano (SA), Italy.

Email: formato@udsab.dia.unisa.it

³ Rank Xerox Research Centre, Grenoble Laboratory
6, chemin de Maupertuis. F-38240 Meylan, France.

Email: {borghoff,pareschi}@xerox.fr

Abstract Distributed Problem Solving (DPS) decomposes problems into subproblems to be solved by interacting, cooperative software agents. Thus, DPS is suitable for modeling, in the context of parallel and distributed architectures, the solving of problems characterized by many inter-dependencies among subproblems. Concurrent Constraint Programming (CCP) provides a powerful execution framework for DPS, where constraints can declaratively implement both local problem solving as well as exchange of information, and hence DPS, among agents. To optimize DPS, the protocol for constraint communication must be tuned to the specific kind of DPS problem and the characteristics of the underlying system architecture. In this paper, we provide a formal framework for modeling different options and we show how it applies to concrete, generalizable examples.

Key words: constraint propagation, distributed artificial intelligence, distributed problem solving, constraint-based knowledge brokers, cooperative agents, protocols.

1 Introduction

As a discipline, Distributed Problem Solving (DPS) arises naturally with the coming of age of distributed and parallel architectures. From a problem solving point of view, distribution implies the decomposition of a problem into a set of subproblems, where the solution of the problem amounts to concurrently solving all of the subproblems and then composing their solutions. Subproblems are solved by parallel processes, or by dynamic software agents in networked environments. As characterized in [23], if there are many inter-dependencies among the subproblems (and thus the agents assigned to solve them must interact a great deal) then we pass from simple distributed processing into the realm of true DPS. For instance, gathering information from distributed knowledge repositories in the context of executing a complex plan belongs to DPS: information gathered as part of a certain task in the plan may typically influence other tasks.

Concurrent Constraint Programming (CCP) is a powerful framework to support DPS, since it provides a direct implementation of the notion of shared, reusable, incrementally refined information. To optimally solve DPS problems with CCP however, we need capabilities for tuning the scope of the communication at the execution level by taking into account such factors as the specific instance of the DPS problem and the characteristics of the underlying system architecture. Specifically, we need to be able to determine how many agents can make use of, and thus should be exposed to given information in the form of constraints. In this paper we shall first introduce a constraint-based protocol for DPS under the hypothesis of *minimal* reuse: all generated information is made potentially available, but it can be delivered only in response to specific requests. We shall then

consider the opposite approach, based on the idea of *maximal* reuse: in this case, all generated information is immediately broadcast to all agents. This decreases the amount of network traffic, as the complications of the request-based protocol are avoided (deliveries being done once and forever) but risks cluttering agents with useless information. In the course of the paper, we shall formally introduce the notion of *quantity of reuse* of information to obtain a heuristics providing a criterion of choice between the two protocols.

This paper aims at breaking ground on a subject whose full development will rely on future work. For instance, it is quite possible to define “intermediate” protocols where automatic deliveries are done for subsets of agents. For many practical applications these cases will be the most useful, so we need techniques for assigning agents to appropriate “interest groups”, to allow flexible tuning of constraint-based communication. Furthermore, we shall observe by simple but generalizable examples that the optimal solution of a DPS problem may involve splitting the problem into subproblems which are optimally solved according to different protocols. Again, we need techniques for guessing the right “chemistry” of protocols for each particular case.

Our study of protocols for constraint-based communication is done within the Constraint-Based Knowledge Broker (CBKB) model [1], a recently introduced formalization of CCP where a sharp separation is drawn between the use of constraints for, (1) local problem solving and (2) communication. Compared to other formalizations of CCP, the CBKB model focuses more directly on communication issues, and hence on problem solving done via the interaction of cooperative agents.

Organization of the paper. Sect. 2 outlines the main characteristics of the specification language *LO* that is used to specify the DPS protocols. Sect. 3 introduces the Constraint-Based Knowledge Broker model (CBKB), a formal framework for CCP. The CBKB framework is used to formalize and compare two different DPS protocols, based, respectively, on the *minimal* and the *maximal* reuse of generated results. In Sect. 4, an analysis follows where the notion of *quantity of reuse* is exploited to determine whether the protocol with minimal or maximal reuse, or even a hybrid approach, is appropriate. Concrete examples are illustrated where advantages and disadvantages of both protocols are made evident. In Sect. 5, related work is discussed, and finally, Sect. 6 concludes by addressing future work.

2 A Declarative, Executable Specification Language: *LO*

As a specification language for our DPS protocols we use *LO* [3], a declarative concurrent language which amalgamates aspects of concurrent languages based on generative communication, such as *CHAM* [6], *Gamma* [5], *Linda* [8], *Swarm* [25], as well as of concurrent logic programming languages [9, 10, 15, 19, 32]. *LO*'s logical primitives for agent coordination and communication make it particularly suitable for our purposes; on the other hand, our approach is compatible with other choices of a specification language.

The *LO* programming constructs are rules that define interaction among concurrent agents. Agents are seen as pools of tokens where a pool is represented as a multiset of these tokens. There are three basic constructs in *LO*:

- The @-construct is used to manage intra-pool concurrency. It is used in rules of the form

a @ b <>- c @ d

meaning that a and b have both to be present in the pool before application of the rule and are both withdrawn from the pool after application. Moreover c and d are present in the pool after application.

- The &-construct is used to manage inter-pool concurrency. It is used in rules of the form

a @ b <>- c & d

meaning that a and b have both to be present in the pool before application of the rule and are both withdrawn from the pool after application. Moreover two new pools are created by replicating the remaining tokens in the pool and adding c to one of the created pools and d to the other.

- The $\hat{\cdot}$ -construct is used to broadcast tokens among agents. It is used in rules of the form

$$a @ b @ \hat{c} \langle \rangle - d$$

meaning that a and b have both to be present in the pool before application of the rule and are both withdrawn from the pool after application. Moreover, after application d is present in the pool and c is present in any pool different from the one in which the rule has been applied.⁴

Tokens can be *indexed* so as to restrict broadcasting to multicasting up to the degenerate case of one-to-one communication. Indices allow linking of senders and receivers over specific tokens: indexed tokens are sent only to agents that are “registered” for that index. Indexing and deindexing of tokens will be the crucial means for differentiating the DPS protocols that will be specified in the course of the paper.

Rules are triggered via pattern matching. The state of a pool is matched against the left-hand sides of rules. When a match is found, the selected rule is applied, *i.e.* the tokens in its left-hand side are removed from the pool, broadcast tokens are transmitted to other pools, and new multisets are defined according to the right-hand side of the rule. For a formal operational semantics for *LO*, based on the proof theory of *Linear Logic* [14], see [3].

3 A Formal Framework for DPS

We can formalize the problem-subproblem relationship, which is at the basis of DPS, via the notion of *generator*. Intuitively, a generator defines the subproblems which need to be solved in order to solve a given problem. A generator works by formalizing problem solving in terms of stable models and fixed-point operators. *Constraints* provide a declarative way to prune the search space of agents.

Generators. Given an abstract domain of values \mathcal{D} , representing tokens of knowledge, a *generator* is a mapping $\mathcal{D}^n \mapsto \wp(\mathcal{D})$, which produces new tokens from existing ones. A set of generators identifies a class of subsets of the domain which are stable by these generators. Let E be a subset of the domain and Γ a set of generators.

Definition 1 E is called Γ -stable if and only if $\forall g \in \Gamma, \forall a_1, \dots, a_n \in E, g(a_1, \dots, a_n) \subset E$.

The class of stable sets is closed under intersection, so that it has a smallest element in the sense of inclusion, given by the intersection of all the stable sets. This minimal stable set, also called *minimal model*, represents the intended semantics of the set of generators. The class of stable sets is also closed under non-decreasing union, so that a standard fixed-point procedure can be applied to compute the minimal model. The core of the procedure is given by the mapping: $T : \wp(\mathcal{D}) \mapsto \wp(\mathcal{D})$ where $\forall E \in \wp(\mathcal{D}) : T(E) = \bigcup_{\substack{g \in \Gamma \\ a_1, \dots, a_n \in E}} g(a_1, \dots, a_n)$.

Minimal model. The minimal model M is then given by the least fixed-point of T , expressed as $M = \bigcup_{n \in \mathbb{N}} T^n(\emptyset)$. Thus, T provides a way of incrementally computing the minimal stable set, by computing the sequence $(T^n(\emptyset))_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$, given by $E_0 = \emptyset$ and $E_{n+1} = T(E_n)$.

⁴A library of higher-level communication facilities on top of the basic mechanism of broadcasting in *LO* is described in [7].

Basic protocol. Generators can be associated with a class of *LO*-agents which we call *broker* agents. A broker realizes a generator function by applying input tokens to it and producing corresponding output tokens. The fixed-point procedure is initialized by putting two special input tokens inside each broker agent. First, the token *arity-n*, where n is a non-negative integer, holds the arity of the generator g , and second, the token *free-k* (for each positive integer k , less than or equal to the arity) represents a place holder, one for each argument of the generator g . These tokens are consumed as arguments get bound.

Constraints. The basic protocol, which relies on a simple forward-chaining scheme, can be refined into protocols appropriate for DPS by taking into account dependencies between the input and output tokens of different broker agents' generators. Two such refinements are illustrated in the next two sections. In both cases, we rely on the idea that a broker agent has some knowledge of the dependency between the input and output tokens of its associated generator, so that it is capable, given a *constraint* on the outputs (the constraint given by a *request*), to infer constraints on the inputs. Thus, constraints provide top-down filtering over the set of values that can be produced by a generator as candidate solutions for a given problem, and permit the exploitation of inter-dependencies between subproblems.

More formally, let us consider the mapping $\bar{g} : \wp(\mathcal{D}) \mapsto \wp(\mathcal{D}^n)$ defined by: $\forall w \in \wp(\mathcal{D})$, $\bar{g}(w) = \prod_{k=1}^n \bar{g}_k(w)$ (note that, in order to infer constraints on the inputs, $\bar{g}_k(w)$, the back-dependency function for argument position k , must be known). By definition, we have: $\forall \vec{a} \in \mathcal{D}^n$, $\forall w \in \wp(\mathcal{D})$, if $g(\vec{a}) \cap w \neq \emptyset$ then $\vec{a} \in \bar{g}(w)$. If \mathcal{G} denotes the graph of a generator g (hence $\mathcal{G} \in \wp(\mathcal{D}^{n+1})$), then we have equivalently, $\forall w \in \wp(\mathcal{D})$, $\mathcal{G} \cap (\mathcal{D}^n \times w) \subset (\bar{g}(w) \times w)$.

In other words, $\bar{g}(w) \times w$ provides an upper approximation (in the sense of inclusion) of the part of the set $(\mathcal{D}^n \times w)$ which is contained in the graph of the generator. To capture inter-argument dependencies, we generalize this notion of approximation, and we assume that each broker is equipped not only with a generator g but also with an *inter-dependency* function. The inter-dependency function computes an upper approximation of the part of any subset of \mathcal{D}^{n+1} which is included in the graph of the generator.

We illustrate this behavior through Fig. 1. The body of this figure shows graphically how inter-dependencies in the activities of broker agents are exploited to feed the generator's function with the needed input tokens.

Figure 1: Exploiting inter-dependencies.

Scope of a broker. We define the *scope* of a broker as the subset of the domain which does not intersect any of the constraints of the requests it has already processed. In other words, the scope of a broker denotes the complement of the set of elements of the minimal model the broker (or one of its clones) has already explicitly generated (or is in the process of generating). A broker can be viewed as an agent which explores the domain and explicitly generates the elements it encounters which are in the minimal model. The scope of the broker denotes the un-explored area of the domain.

Let w_o be the scope of a broker at some point, and let w be the constraint of a request it receives.

The broker spawns an agent in charge of exploring the subset $w_o \cap w$ (and answering the request), and itself continues with a reduced scope $w_o \cap \neg w$ (where $\neg w$ is the complement of w).

3.1 The Request-Subrequest Protocol

The request-subrequest protocol refines constraint-based communication as illustrated in the section above by exploiting yet another dependency: the request carries an index that is added to all output tokens that are sent out. In this way, requester and requestee are directly linked. Information is provided only if requested, and is sent only to the original requester.

The initial request carries an index which acts as an address for the requesting agents, as well as a description of the problem to be solved (instantiated as a constraint on the problem domain). A broker agent takes the problem description and simplifies it into subproblems. These descriptions of the subproblems are then submitted as subrequests in the same way as the initial request. The subrequests are individually indexed so that they can be collected into a solution by the requestee agents which is eventually returned to the original requesters.

LO-encoding of the request-subrequest protocol.

(RS1) broker(W0) @ requ(Index,W) @ split(W0,W,W1,W2) @ init(W1,S)
 <>- broker(W2) & process @ requ(Index,W) @ const(S).

The token `split(w_o, w, w_1, w_2)` defines, given two subsets w_o, w of \mathcal{D} , the subsets w_1, w_2 of \mathcal{D} defined by $w_1 = w_o \cap w$ and $w_2 = w_o \cap \neg w$. The pattern `init- n` is used to compute the initial approximation: the token `init- n (w, s)` builds, given a subset w of \mathcal{D} , the subset s of \mathcal{D}^{n+1} defined as $s = \tilde{g}(\mathcal{D}^n \times w)$. It is assumed that if s is empty, the token is not present. The index `Index` of a request acts as an address for the requester.

(RS2) const(S) @ free-k @ seek-k(S,W) @ ^requ(Index,W)
 <>- const(S) @ wait-k(Index) @ requ(Index,W).

The pattern `seek- k` is used to extract information from an approximation (by simple projection). The token `seek- k (s, w)` builds, given a subset s of \mathcal{D}^{n+1} , the subset w of \mathcal{D} defined as $w = \pi_k < s >$. The agent sends an indexed subrequest for the subproblem specified by w .

(RS3) const(S) @ wait-k(Index) @ answer(Index,X) @ ins-k(X,S,S')
 <>- const(S) @ wait-k(Index) & const(S') @ bound-k(X).

The patterns `ins- k` provide further refinements of the approximation upon receiving answers to the subrequests. The token `ins- k (x, s, s')` builds, given a subset s of \mathcal{D}^{n+1} and an element x of \mathcal{D} , the subset s' of \mathcal{D}^{n+1} defined as $s' = \tilde{g}(s \cap \pi_k^{-1} < x >)$. In other words, s' is the approximation of the subset of s consisting of the tuples which are in the graph of the generator and whose k -th component is precisely x . Thus, the binding of the k -th argument may reduce the scope of the other arguments. It is assumed here that if s' is empty, the token is not present.

(RS4) arity-n @ bound-1(X1) @ ... @ bound-n(Xn) <>- tuple-n(X1,...,Xn).

The broker agent feeds the generator's function with input tokens of the corresponding arity.

(RS5) process @ res(X) <>- process & process(X).

Creates a process that is in charge of a specific result `res(X)`.

(RS6) process(X) @ requ(Index,W) @ sat(X,W) @ ^answer(Index,X)
 <>- process(X).

Send out the answer using the index `Index`. The pattern `sat` is needed for consistency reasons: the token `sat(X,W)` simply checks whether a partial result `X` complies with the given constraint `W`.

The request-subrequest protocol does not avoid redundancies in subproblem generation due to recursive pattern. Suppose a broker has a generator g with $g(t) = \{t\}$ and receives a request with a constraint w such that $t \in w$. A specialized agent A is created to process this request. Suppose furthermore that the initial problem (constraint) $\hat{g}(\mathcal{D} \times w)$, returned by the token `init`, is $s = w \times w$. Now, since $\pi_1 \langle s \rangle = w$, the subrequest for the (single) argument of the generator also has w as constraint. The same broker receives this subrequest (sent by A) and spawns again a new agent in charge of the same request for an already requested subproblem.

Another, related, issue is that of reuse. Suppose that two brokers generate subrequests with the same constraint (or overlapping constraint). With the basic request-subrequest protocol, these two requests are processed separately, *i.e.*, all the work of generation of explicit elements of the minimal model satisfying the constraint of the requests is duplicated (at least partially).

3.2 The Local Caching Protocol

The local caching protocol does not link requesters with requestees. By contrast, as soon as a solution for a particular subproblem is available, it is broadcast to all existing broker agents.

The initial request carries only a description of the problem to be solved; no index is associated with it. As before, a broker agent takes the problem description and simplifies it into subproblems. However, as a consequence of this protocol, for some of the subproblems solutions may already be known to the broker agents. The description of yet unsolved subproblems are then submitted as subrequests in the same way as the initial request, *i.e.*, again without index. In this way, we obtain a situation of local *caching* of information for all existing broker instantiations, thus decreasing the overall amount of traffic, as we avoid the re-generation of the same requests from different requesters. On the other hand, we may end up storing information which never gets used.

In general, this approach is appropriate when there are several requests of the same item, or when the available architecture does not support large amount of communication traffic.

LO-encoding of the local caching protocol.

(LC1) `broker(W0) @ requ(W) @ split(W0,W,W1,W2) @ init(W1,S)`
`<>- broker(W2) & process @ requ(W) @ const(S).`

The request carries no index.

(LC2) `const(S) @ free-k @ no_answer_sat(Mset_X,S) @ seek-k(S,W) @ ^requ(W)`
`<>- const(S) @ requ(W).`

If the solution to the subproblem for W is not yet obtained (*i.e.* the pattern of the predicate `no_answer_sat(Mset_X,S)` holds), the agent sends a deindexed subrequest. The predicate `no_answer_sat(Mset_X,S)` checks the multiset of already obtained results; if and only if none of the elements of `Mset_X` complies with the given constraint, the predicate holds.⁵

(LC3) `const(S) @ answer(X) @ sat(X,S) @ ins-k(X,S,S')`
`<>- const(S) & const(S') @ bound-k(X).`

If a partial result X is (already) obtained that complies with the given constraint S , the `answer(X)` is (re-) used.

(LC4) `arity-n @ bound-1(X1) @ ... @ bound-n(Xn) <>- tuple-n(X1,...,Xn).`

⁵Even if an answer arrives which complies with the given constraint S but is not checked by the predicate `no_answer_sat(Mset_X,S)` in time, the only drawback is that a redundant subrequest will be generated. Effective handling of negative information of this kind is a well-known problem in concurrent programming, for which first results can be found in [27].

(LC5) $\text{process} @ \text{res}(X) \langle \rangle - \text{process} \ \& \ \text{process}(X)$.

This method generates a new token in the pool representing the “memory” of the broker. It can be reused by triggering the next rule, whose task is checking whether the answer produced by the generator contained in token $\text{res}(X)$ satisfies the constraint W . Eventually, the token is broadcast to all existing broker agents, by means of the unindexed token $\text{answer}(X)$.

(LC6) $\text{process}(X) @ \text{requ}(W) @ \text{sat}(X, W) @ \hat{\text{answer}}(X) \langle \rangle - \text{process}(X)$.

The generated token is cached in $\text{process}(X)$ and is broadcast to all other agents.

4 Analysis of Reuse of Information in the two Protocols

In this section, we compare the behavior of request-subrequest and local caching from the point of view of the reuse of information. In particular, we shall substantiate the hypothesis that local caching performs better than request-subrequest when (and only when) reuse of partial results is high.

To facilitate the comparison, we introduce the notion of a *measure of reuse* R in terms of the number of the partial results that can be reused. Thus, R will provide a heuristic for the choice of the appropriate protocol. High values of R suggest choosing the local caching protocol, while low values of R indicate using the request-subrequest protocol.

4.1 Domain of the Analysis

To be as explicit as possible, we define R for two domains given: one, the set of propositional formulas, and the second the algebra of closed first-order terms.

Propositional formulas. The value R gives a measure of the reusability of tokens in the generation of a well-formed propositional formula, by counting the number of occurrences of the same subformula in a given propositional formula.

Definition 2 *Let α and β represent well-formed propositional formulas, and let Λ stand for a possibly empty multiset of formulas. Let $\{A_1, A_2, \dots, A_n\}$ represent a set of propositional atomic formulas. Furthermore, let $m(A_i)$ express the multiplicity of occurrences of A_i in $\{A_1, A_2, \dots, A_n\}$.*

$$\begin{aligned}
 R(\{\alpha \vee \beta\} \cup \Lambda) &= R(\{\alpha, \beta\} \cup \Lambda) \\
 R(\{\alpha \vee \alpha\} \cup \Lambda) &= R(\{\alpha, \alpha\} \cup \Lambda) + 2 \\
 R(\{\alpha \wedge \beta\} \cup \Lambda) &= R(\{\alpha, \beta\} \cup \Lambda) \\
 R(\{\alpha \wedge \alpha\} \cup \Lambda) &= R(\{\alpha, \alpha\} \cup \Lambda) + 2 \\
 R(\{\neg\alpha\} \cup \Lambda) &= R(\{\alpha\} \cup \Lambda) \\
 R(\{A_1, \dots, A_n\}) &= \sum_{\substack{A_i \in \{A_1, \dots, A_n\} \\ \text{where } m(A_i) > 1}} m(A_i)
 \end{aligned}$$

We give now an example of two formulas with the same number of propositional atomic formulas where the measure of reuse R is low in the former and high in the latter:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \alpha_m &= A_1 \vee (A_2 \vee (A_3 \vee A_4)) \\
 \alpha_M &= (A_1 \vee A_1) \vee (A_1 \vee A_1)
 \end{aligned}$$

In the first case, the value of reuse $R(\{\alpha_m\})$ is 0 (no reuse at all), while in the second the value of reuse $R(\{\alpha_M\})$ is 10 (the maximum value of reuse for a formula of length 4).

At first glance, the definition of the measure of reuse looks rather arbitrary. However, in the following it will smoothly fit in a more general domain.

Algebra of closed first-order terms. We give now a definition of R for the case where the minimal model is an algebra of closed first-order terms. As can be seen easily,⁶ this definition generalizes Definition 2.

Definition 3 Let Λ indicate a possibly empty multiset of terms in a signature and let $\{a_1, \dots, a_n\}$ represent a set of constants. Furthermore, let $m(t_i)$ express the multiplicity of occurrences of term t_i in the multiset $\{t_1, \dots, t_n\}$, and $m(a_i)$ express the multiplicity of occurrences of constant a_i in the multiset $\{a_1, \dots, a_n\}$.

$$R(\{f(t_1, \dots, t_n)\} \cup \Lambda) = R(\{t_1, \dots, t_n\} \cup \Lambda) + \sum_{\substack{t_i \in \{t_1, \dots, t_n\} \\ \text{where } m(t_i) > 1}} m(t_i)$$

$$R(\{a_1, \dots, a_n\}) = \sum_{\substack{a_i \in \{a_1, \dots, a_n\} \\ \text{where } m(a_i) > 1}} m(a_i)$$

Analogously to before, we give an example of two terms with the same number of constants where we obtain two different values for the measure of reuse:

$$t_m = f(a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4)$$

$$t_M = f(f(a_1, a_1), f(a_1, a_1))$$

In the former case, the value of reuse $R(\{t_m\})$ is 0 (no reuse at all), while in the second the value of reuse $R(\{t_M\})$ is 10 (the maximum value of reuse for a term of length 4; note that, $R(\{f(t_1, \dots, t_n)\}) = R(\{f(f(t_1, \dots, t_n))\})$).

4.2 Example for the Reuse in the Local Caching Protocol

We present now an example of reuse of information in the local caching protocol, in the case of the generation of the minimal model of an algebra of closed first-order terms under the constraint w represented by the set of terms $t \in \mathcal{T}$ whose length $L(t)$ is not more than 3.

Let g be a generator of arity 2. According to the computational model that takes into account the inter-dependencies of the tokens of the generators, we take as \tilde{g} the following function mapping $\wp(\mathcal{T}^3)$ into itself: $\tilde{g}((t_1, t_2, t_3)) = \{(t_1, t_2, t_3) \in \mathcal{T}^3 \mid (t_1, t_2) \in \mathcal{T}^2 \text{ and } t_3 = g(t_1, t_2)\}$.

It can be immediately verified that \tilde{g} satisfies the properties of the approximating function described in [1] as: $\tilde{g} : \wp(\mathcal{D}^{n+1}) \mapsto \wp(\mathcal{D}^{n+1})$ where $\forall s \in \wp(\mathcal{D}^{n+1}) : \mathcal{G} \cap s \subset \tilde{g}(s)$.

Thus, the inter-dependency function computes an upper approximation of the part of any subset of \mathcal{D}^{n+1} which is included in the graph of the generator. Being an approximation function, we assume that \tilde{g} has the usual (anti-)closure properties, *i.e.*, it is reductive, monotonous and idempotent, *i.e.*

$$\forall s, s_1, s_2, \quad \begin{cases} \tilde{g}(s) \subset s \\ \text{if } s_1 \subset s_2 \text{ then } \tilde{g}(s_1) \subset \tilde{g}(s_2) \\ \tilde{g}(\tilde{g}(s)) = \tilde{g}(s) \end{cases}$$

As we have defined \tilde{g} , the semantics of the patterns `ins- k` of rule (LC3) and `init` of rule (LC1) are well defined. Let us now analyze the flow of messages in the local caching protocol: a broker is given initially the scope $w_0 = \{t \in \mathcal{T} \mid L(t) \leq 3\}$. Suppose it receives the request `requ(w)` where $w = \{t \in \mathcal{T} \mid L(t) \leq 2\}$. As explained before, the pattern `split` produces two new sets w_1 and w_2 . In our example, it immediately follows that $w_1 = w_0 \cap w = w$ and $w_2 = w_0 \cap \neg w = \{t \in \mathcal{T} \mid L(t) = 3\}$. Besides, the pattern `init` will set $s = \{t \in \mathcal{T} \mid L(t) \leq 2\}$. By triggering the rule (LC1), a new agent will be spawned, whose scope will be s .

Let us focus our attention on this new agent. Suppose tokens `seek-1` and `free-1` are already present in the agent's set of states; then, token `seek-1` will activate the back-dependency function

⁶*e.g.*, by interpreting ' \vee ' and ' \wedge ' as functions of arity 2, and seeing propositional atomic formulas as constants.

on constraint s , establishing a constraint over the arguments. Notice that since $L(t) \leq 2$, the back-dependency function will deliver a subrequest to a zero-ary or unary broker. This will produce a subrequest to another agent, encoded as the argument of the token `requ`. If the answer to this request is already present in the broker's local storage, encoded as the argument of the token `answer`, then rule (LC3) will be triggered, producing instantiation of the first argument and the generation of the answer to the initial request w . The argument of `answer` could have been generated by the broker itself during a past computation, and then broadcast (see rule (LC6)) to all existing brokers.

4.3 Comparing Reuse in the Two Protocols

Both the request-subrequest and the local caching protocol provide support for reusing already generated results. The main difference between the two protocols is that local caching allows a structured possibility of reuse, *i.e.*, it automatically binds the new results of a generator with the results that are already known. By contrast, the request-subrequest protocol offers just memory, namely the bare possibility of storing the results by the simple persistence of the token `process` (X) in the state of the requestee broker (see rule (RS6)).

Figure 2: Comparison of the message flow in the both protocols.

This difference in behavior is illustrated through the example of Fig. 2, where a broker associated with a generator g of arity 2 asks two other brokers a request of the same kind; these ones, in turn, ask two other brokers a subrequest to generate tokens a and b . The request-subrequest protocol allows a simple form of reuse, amounting to storing the partial results a and b in the requestee broker that can then redeliver such results upon new requests without newly generating them. By contrast, the local caching protocol allows a thorough reuse of results, shifting all the computational load to the broker associated with the generator g . Generators for a and b send their answer to g that yields $g(a, b)$; this token is returned in a deindexed fashion and reaches all existing brokers, that can use it to build the new token $g(g(a, b), g(a, b))$. The local caching protocol's structured reuse reduces dramatically the number of brokers involved, even though the deindexed message flow characteristic of local caching produces in some cases a bundle of wasted messages.

We use the case of propositional formulas as an example for comparing the two protocols. Through this example, we can also observe how it is sometimes appropriate to use a hybrid scheme, *i.e.* by subdividing a problem into subproblems solved with different protocols.

Context-free grammar. Let us consider parsing of context-free grammars as a class of DPS problems. It is well-known that these problems generalize easily to problems of deductive querying [24] and hence, in a distributed world, to problems of information gathering [23].

Some of these parsing problems may involve brokers that produce output reused as input by many other brokers, as well as by themselves. This is typically the case when we are dealing with ambiguous expressions. Take for instance the following recursive ambiguous context-free grammar G for generating boolean expressions, where with the symbol F we denote a generic propositional formula, with A an atomic formula, and with a, b, c and d we denote four particular atomic formulas.

$$\begin{aligned} S &\Rightarrow F \\ F &\Rightarrow A \mid F \vee F \mid F \wedge F \mid \neg F \mid (F) \\ A &\Rightarrow a \mid b \mid c \mid d \end{aligned}$$

Let $\tilde{\alpha}$ be an ambiguous propositional formula and M the set of parsed trees generated by the grammar, we denote with $M_{\tilde{\alpha}}$ the set of parsed trees having $\tilde{\alpha}$ as leaf. The cardinality of $M_{\tilde{\alpha}}$ is given by the $(n-1)$ -th number of Catalan C_{n-1} ,⁷ where n is the number of atomic formulas in $\tilde{\alpha}$, *i.e.*:⁸

$$|M_{\tilde{\alpha}}| = C_{n-1}.$$

For example, let $\tilde{\alpha}$ be $a \vee b \wedge c \vee d$. Then, we get $M_{\tilde{\alpha}} = \{((a \vee b) \wedge (c \vee d)), (a \vee (b \wedge (c \vee d))), (a \vee ((b \wedge c) \vee d)), (((a \vee b) \wedge c) \vee d), ((a \vee (b \wedge c)) \vee d)\}$, and hence $|M_{\tilde{\alpha}}| = C_3 = 5$.

The rest of this section deals with the average quantity of reuse and proves a helpful theorem.

Quantity μ_n . Let M_n be the set of propositional well-formed formulas with n atomic formulas yielded by the grammar G . Thus, the quantity

$$\mu_n = \frac{\sum_{\alpha \in M_n} R(\{\alpha\})}{|M_n|}$$

gives the average value for the measure of reuse R in the domain of well-formed propositional formulas of length n . According to its value, the quantity μ_n supplies us with a reliable criterion for deciding which of the two protocols is more suitable for implementing the CBKB model in the domain of the well-formed formulas without variables.

More generally, given a minimal model $M_n = T^n(\emptyset)$ (where T is the fixed-point operator for the construction of the minimal model M), and using a reuse measure R defined for all $m \in M_n$, the average quantity of reuse can be generalized to

$$\mu_n = \frac{\sum_{m \in M_n} R(\{m\})}{|M_n|}$$

Language $L(G)$. For the sake of simplicity, we now define the least equivalence relation \simeq on the language $L(G)$ generated by the grammar G (which contains the following relation \sim) where α stands for a propositional well-formed formula:

$$\begin{aligned} ((\neg)^n \alpha) &\sim \alpha \quad , \text{ if } n \text{ is even} \\ ((\neg)^n \alpha) &\sim \neg(\alpha) \quad , \text{ if } n \text{ is odd} \end{aligned}$$

Now consider

$$L(G)^\simeq = \frac{L(G)}{\simeq}.$$

Since we can simplify $L(G)$ to the quotient language $L(G)^\simeq$ without loss of generality (as $\neg\neg\alpha \leftrightarrow \alpha$ holds in classical logic), we can prove a theorem which shows a nice relation between the measure of reuse R , as introduced at the beginning of the section, and the number of Catalan:

⁷ $C_n = \frac{(2n)!}{n!(n+1)!}$.

⁸This holds, since we can set a bijection between the binary trees with n leaves and the ways of putting parentheses to a word of length n (see [20] for details).

Theorem 1 Let $L(G)_n^\neg$ be the set of wffs in $L(G)^\neg$ having n atomic occurrences, and let ϕ be the number of different atomic formulas in the grammar G , then $|L(G)_n^\neg| = C_{n-1}\phi^n 2^{3n-2}$.

Proof. Let T be a binary tree representing the parse of a formula with n atomic occurrences. Obviously, the number of nodes of T is $2n - 1$, and the total number of inner nodes (*i.e.*, nodes that are not leaves) is $(2n - 1) - n = n - 1$. Now there will be only two ways of generating a propositional well-formed formula from the tree T . Briefly,

1. since every inner node is binary, and since a propositional formula has only two binary connectives (' \vee ' and ' \wedge '), there are 2^{n-1} ways of placing these connectives to the formula.
2. since the double negation is absorbed by a blank, there are $\sum_{i=0}^{2n-1} \binom{2n-1}{i} (= 2^{2n-1})$ ways of adding the negation symbol ($i = 0$ represents the case where no negation symbol is set).

It is easy to see that there is a bijection between the binary trees generated in this way and the propositional well-formed formulas of $L(G)^\neg$. Since there are C_{n-1} different binary trees and only ϕ^n different dispositions of ϕ atomic formulas into n atomic occurrences, the claim follows. **q.e.d.**

By Theorem 1, we have a refinement of the quantity μ_n defining the average value for the measure of reuse R , namely

$$\mu_n = \frac{\sum_{\alpha \in M_n} R(\{\alpha\})}{|M_n|}$$

where

$$|M_n| = C_{n-1}\phi^n 2^{3n-2}$$

Refinements of the same kind for the quantity of reuse can be defined for a number of other cases, thus providing a solid formal basis for the choice of the appropriate protocol. In the next section, however, we shall compare, on specific parsing examples, the two protocols in a less formal way, by means of graphical representations illustrating the flow of messages among broker agents.

4.4 Discussion

Request-subrequest protocol. While local caching would seem in general appropriate for parsing boolean expressions with the grammar above, there are cases where request-subrequest is instead preferable.

As shown in Fig. 3, in the generation of the parse tree for the formula $\alpha = ((a \wedge b) \wedge (c \vee d))$ where only little reuse of previous partial results is possible, the request-subrequest protocol is the right choice. As shown in the grey box of the '*and*'-broker's generator for the partial result $(c \vee d)$, the possible reuse of information is low, and as a consequence the use of the local caching protocol is not recommended.

Local caching protocol. The local caching protocol is particularly appropriate when parsing formulas with multiple occurrences of the same subformulas, as in the case of the formula $\alpha = ((a \wedge a) \wedge (a \wedge a))$.⁹ This aspect is put in evidence in Fig. 4 by showing the traffic among brokers agents during the generation of α . Solid lines represent messages which are effectively used in constructing the token, while dashed lines stand for broadcast messages which could possibly get wasted.

⁹The case of a boolean formula with multiple occurrences of the same subformula can be thought as an abstract version of many real-life examples, where the same piece of information is used all over again in different places. Consider for example a hyper-document where *e.g.* all Xerox copiers are described in terms of specification, costs, suppliers, references, table of comparisons, other company's products, etc. Obviously, the same pieces of information (*e.g.*, price list, vendor addresses, warranty text, Xerox logo and Xerox common information, ...) are reused in most of the documents of this sort. In a hyper-document, typically, there are many links that point to these pieces of information. Likely reuse of this information during a browsing session suggests local caching as the appropriate protocol.

Figure 3: Message flow during parsing of a formula with possible reuse.

Figure 4: Message flow in the local caching protocol with two broker agents.

The broker agent in charge of a sends a to the ‘*and*’-broker’s generator which binds (and reuses) this argument to generate $(a \wedge a)$; finally, this new token is again reused and bound twice for the generation of the token $((a \wedge a) \wedge (a \wedge a))$. This is a significant case of reuse, obtained at the price of a bundle of possibly wasted messages.

Fig. 5 focuses on the growing of broadcast messages as the number of brokers increases. It contains an overwhelming bundle of messages, very few of which (printed in solid lines) are effectively used for the generation of the token $((a \vee b) \wedge (a \vee b))$. Here the ‘*and*’-broker’s generator can benefit of the deindexation of answer because both pools containing the tokens `free-1` and `free-2` receive the partial result $(a \vee b)$, causing the generator to yield the answer.

5 Related work

This paper relates directly to previous results published in [1] where the notion of Constraint Based Knowledge Broker was first introduced. More recent work on the CBKB model [2] has provided a number of complexity results concerning the number of agents needed in the request-subrequest protocol, and the number of messages sent, both in the form of requests and of answers. These results have directly influenced the idea of investigating different protocols, so as to handle a variety of problem domains and system architectures.

Figure 5: Message flow in the local caching protocol with four broker agents.

For a conceptual characterization of Distributed Problem Solving see [12, 13]. The well-known Contract Net Protocol [31] is an opportunist coordination approach using negotiations among distributed agents as its central interaction mechanism for DPS. More recently, a cooperative information gathering approach using a multi-agent system based on DPS has been illustrated in [23]. Additional relevant literature can be found in [21]. Cooperative Solutions for Constraint Satisfaction Problems have been addressed in [11] where quantitative measures (*e.g.* time to solution distributions) based on experiments are given. However, so far DPS has been missing a real computational model, and our work can be seen as a first contribution to fill this gap.

Concurrent Constraint Programming, the background for our CBKB model, was introduced in [26], by applying to concurrent programming the insights gained through Constraint Logic Programming [16, 18]. There, a process transition is controlled by the presence of a constraint in the constraint store, or, more precisely, by its entailment from the constraint store. This enforces a strictly monotonous view of constraints, which has been partially relaxed in [28] (for a similar kind of relaxation, see also [17]). This approach does not make the distinction between two different uses of constraints: for local problem solving and for communication (and hence for Distributed Problem Solving). By contrast, this distinction appears clearly in the CBKB model, where communication of constraints is achieved via the global flow of messages while each individual broker agent encapsulates its own local problem solver. Thus, our approach can also be seen as a contribution to merging the two paradigms of Concurrent Constraint Programming and of Coordination Languages [8], where a coordination language is seen as the layer for glueing together independent software components to perform a global activity.

An early contribution in this direction (dating well before the programming paradigms of both Concurrent Constraint Programming and Coordination Languages) can be found in [22], where a framework is proposed in which a set of constraints is solved by a system of cooperative, distributed, specialized constraint solvers which exchange their relevant results. This framework is based on a simple broadcast mechanism for constraint propagation, without further investigations on refinements, variations and complexity of this basic protocol.

6 Conclusions and Future Developments

Flexible Tuning. Obviously, the two protocols compared here are at the very opposite ends of a spectrum of possible protocols (see also [4]). These other protocols define intermediate attitudes towards information, in between the hypotheses of minimal and maximal reuse, and in general will be the more useful for most practical applications. We need flexible ways for expressing such protocols, and for mixing them freely in the overall solution of a problem. In addition, we need ways to guess the right protocol, or the right *melange* of protocols, for specific problems. This calls for contributions from such diverse fields as programming linguistics, learning and simulation.

Architecture. It would also be useful to define a taxonomy of system architectures that could help select the right protocol. For instance, transputers seem particularly well-suited for the request-subrequest protocol, as the cost of communication is low and there are strong limitations on storage. By contrast, for distributed architecture based, say, on networks of workstations, local caching would appear as the most appropriate solution.

Combinatorial Analysis. As we have pointed out, our example of context-free parsing as an instance of DPS can be generalized to problems of distributed query processing and information gathering (through the insight of [24]). Thus, context-free parsing could be used as an abstraction for a class of important DPS problems. Under this assumption, one could study the reuse of information from the point of view of asymptotical combinatorial analysis for context-free grammars. This would involve the use of Schützenberger's techniques [29, 30] based on algebraic and transcendental generating functions. These techniques allow the analytical computation of combinatorial quantities relative to the language generated by the grammar, allowing a full (possibly asymptotic) analysis of the reuse.

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